

ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN ENTREPRENEURS OF DAIRY AND BEEKEEPING PRODUCTS: A BIOTIC PERSPECTIVE

45

45

Brîndușa Covaci, Mihai Covaci, Centre for Mountain Economy &
Zealandina Agency - United Kingdom & Australia

Abstract

The manuscript introduces Romanian entrepreneurs engaged in the production of probiotic-rich dairy and beekeeping products within mountainous regions. Probiotic experts affirm the probiotic efficacy of certain dairy and beekeeping items. The document showcases mountain-based producers specializing in fermented dairy products such as yogurt, sana, and kefir, as well as natural honey variants including honeydew (manna), mountain polyflora, coniferous, acacia, and chestnut.

Keywords: beekeeping producers, dairy producers, mountain entrepreneurship

M.C. – conceptualization; B.C. – conceptualization and final

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2021)

Introduction:

Nestled within the breathtaking landscapes of Romania's mountains, a harmonious symphony of entrepreneurial endeavors unfolds, led by resilient individuals who delve into the realms of dairy and beekeeping. This article explores the unique and biotically enriched ventures undertaken by Romanian mountain entrepreneurs, shedding light on the symbiotic relationship between these entrepreneurs, nature, and the products they cultivate.

The Biotic Symphony of Dairy:

In the high-altitude pastures of Romania's mountainous regions, a biotic symphony unfolds as local entrepreneurs engage in the production of dairy products. Beyond the ordinary, these producers infuse their artisanal creations with probiotic richness. Yogurt, sana, and kefir, the staples of Romanian dairy craftsmanship, transcend their traditional roles, becoming not only sources of nutrition but also carriers of beneficial biota.

The fermentation process, a key aspect of these dairy productions, introduces live cultures that contribute to the biotic diversity of the final products. Romanian mountain entrepreneurs take pride in their commitment to preserving local biodiversity and crafting dairy delights that go beyond the ordinary, contributing to the broader narrative of biotic sustenance.

Beekeeping Bliss and Biotic Diversity:

In perfect synergy with their dairy counterparts, Romanian mountain beekeepers engage in the art of apiculture, producing honey that reflects the biotic diversity of the region. Beekeeping practices become a biotic dance, where bees play a crucial role in pollination, fostering the flourishing diversity of mountain flora.

The resulting honey varieties, including honeydew (manna), mountain polyflora, coniferous, acacia, and chestnut, each embody a distinct biotic profile. The geographical and ecological characteristics of the mountains imprint unique flavors and potential probiotic benefits, making these honey varieties not just sweet delights but also carriers of the mountain's biotic essence.

Sustainability in Harmony with Biotic Balance:

Romanian mountain entrepreneurs, custodians of their natural surroundings, understand the delicate equilibrium needed for sustainable practices. The biotic richness of the mountains is not only harnessed but also preserved through eco-conscious approaches. Sustainable beekeeping and dairy production practices contribute to maintaining the biotic balance, ensuring that nature and entrepreneurship coexist harmoniously.

Biotic Innovation and Tradition:

Beyond the economic facets of their endeavors, Romanian mountain entrepreneurs infuse their dairy and beekeeping practices with innovative biotic elements. Probiotics, known for their potential health benefits, become a bridge between tradition and modern wellness trends. These entrepreneurs are at the forefront of biotic innovation, tapping into the growing consumer preference for products that nourish both the body and the surrounding ecosystem.

Conclusion:

Romanian mountain entrepreneurs of dairy and beekeeping products emerge not just as business leaders but as stewards of the biotic richness that defines their landscape. Their commitment to sustainability, biotic innovation, and the preservation of local biodiversity showcases a holistic approach to entrepreneurship. As they continue to cultivate dairy and beekeeping products that resonate with a biotic symphony, these entrepreneurs not only contribute to local economies but also stand as champions of a harmonious coexistence between nature and business.

References

Agenția Națională a Zonei de Munte. 2021. Registrul Național al Produselor Montane. <http://azm.gov.ro/produs-montan/>; accessed on 23.08.2021

Slow Food Foundation for Biodiversity. 2021.

<https://www.fondazione Slow Food.com/en/>

Terra Apis. 2020. Apifitoterapie. www.terraapis.ro

www.gordon.ro

<http://asociatiaapicolastupina.yolasite.com>

http://www.primarialupenihr.ro/prezentare_locala

<http://pomezau.probihor.ro/spinus/38-stupina-popa.html>

ADO – SC Ferma Denis SRL

51

51

Figura A1. Cutie Iaurt ADO 2,8% de cantitate 170 g - lot 1031 (expiră pe 14.10.2021)

Figura A2. Analize fizico-chimice, Iaurt ADO 2,8%

Figura A3. Cutie Iaurt 10% de cantitate 1 Kg – lot 1049 (expiră pe 19.10.2021); analize fizico-chimice

Figura A4. Sticlă Chefir 3,3% de cantitate 0,5 l – lot 1077 (expiră pe 27.10.2021); analize fizico-chimice

Figura A5. Magazin ADO

Figura A6. Produse ADO

Figura A7. Fermă ADO

Figura A8. Produse probiotice ADO

Figura A8. Produse ADO

Figura A9. Magazin ADO

Date de contact:

SC Ferma Denis SRL - Sat Pesteană, Comuna Densus, Nr. 2, Hunedoara;

telefon: +40734779412; e-mail: fermadenis@gmail.com

61

61

Gordon

Figura G1. Compania Gordon

Figura G2. Fermă Gordon

Figura G3. Hală Gordon

Figura G4. Ferma Gordon

Figura G5. Produse probiotice Gordon

Figura G6. Produse Gordon

Figura G7. Produse Gordon

Figura G8. Munții Harghita, zona Gordon

← → ↻ aucthan.ro/store/laurt-Gordon-900-g/p/293126# 🔍 ☆ ⚙️ 📄 B ⋮

CARACTERISTICI PRODUS

Produsul se obtine din lapte pasteurizat, standardizat la 2.8% si insamantat cu cultura termofila.

INFORMATII NUTRITIONALE		INGREDIENTE SI ALERGENI	
kJ pe 100g sau 100ml	227	Ingrediente	Lapte de vaca pasteurizat, culturi lactice selectionate.
kcal pe 100g sau 100ml	54	Alergeni descriere	Lactoza
Grasimi (g sau ml)	2.8		
din care acizi grasi saturati (g sau ml)	1.86		
Glucide (g sau ml)	4.05		
din care zaharuri (g sau ml)	2.29		
Sare (g sau m)	0.32		
Proteine (g sau ml)	3.2		

Feedback

Figura G9. Proprietăți nutriționale și fizico-chimice Iaurt Gordon 2,8%

Sana Gordon 3.6 % grăsime
Greutate: 330g PET

Informații nutriționale medii
per 100g

valoare energetică în kJ și kcal
275 kJ / 66 kcal

grăsimi, g
3.6 g

- din care: acizi grași saturați, g
2.41 g

glucide, g
4.62 g

- din care: zaharuri, g
2.39 g

proteine, g
3.75 g

sare, g
0.32g

Figura G10. Proprietăți nutriționale și fizico-chimice Sana Gordon 3,6%

Kefir Gordon 3.5 % grăsime	
Greutate: 330g PET	
Informații nutriționale medii	
per 100g	
valoare energetică în kJ și kcal	
	275 kJ / 66 kcal
grăsimi, g	3.50g
- din care: acizi grași saturați, g	2.27 g
glucide, g	4.93 g
- din care: zaharuri, g	2.82 g
proteine, g	3.65 g
sare, g	0.12 g

Figura G11. Proprietăți nutriționale și fizico-chimice Kefir Gordon 3,5%

Date de contact:

SC Gordon Prod SRL - Bisericani DN13A 2/A, Harghita; telefoane: relații

clienți - +40266248447, secretariat - +40266248448; e-mail:

office@gordonprod.ro

Popa Tudor Ionuț PFA

Figura PTI1. Stupi Popa Tudor Ionuț PFA

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2021)

Figura PTI2. Stupi Popa Tudor Ionuț PFA

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2021)

Figura PTI3. Stupi Popa Tudor Ionuț PFA

Figura PTI4. Stupi Popa Tudor Ionuț PFA

Figura PTI5. Produse Popa Tudor Ionuț PFA

Date de contact:

Popa Tudor Ionuț PFA - sat Spinuș de Pomezzeu, com. Pomezzeu, nr. 130,

Bihor; telefon: +40744140389; e-mail: popationut@gmail.com

Radu Ion PFA

Figura R1. Stupi și stupine Radu Ion PFA

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2021)

Figura R2. Albine din familiile apicole Radu Ion PFA

Figura R3. Laborator Radu Ion PFA

Figura R4. Laborator Radu Ion PFA

Figura R5. Stupi Radu Ion PFA

Figura R6. Miere de salcâm / polifloră de munte

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2021)

Figura R7. Miere de mană

Figura R3. Arealul montan Masivul Ivănețu

Figura R4. Trovanți din Munții Buzăului

Date de contact:

Radu Ion PFA - Sat. Cozieni, com. Cozieni, Buzău; telefon: +40740237102

Vinereanu Adrian PFA

Figura V1. Miere de mană / munte Vinereanu

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2021)

Figura V2. Stupina Vaideeni

Figura V3. Areal montan Vaideeni

Figura V4. Areal montan Vaideeni

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2021)

Date de contact:

*Vinereanu Adrian PFA - Sat Vaideeni, Comuna Vaideeni, Str. Ciorani, Nr.
10, Vâlcea; telefon: +40747862729; e-mail: vinereanua@yahoo.com*

88

88